

THE FORMATION OF THE IODO DERIVATIVES OF SUBSTITUTED AND BROMO-DISUBSTITUTED MALONAMIDES

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Disubstituted malonamides have been iodinated and monoiodo, diiodo and bromo-iodo derivatives obtained.

Naik and Shah (this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 239) tried to prepare iodo derivatives of substituted malonamides with iodine monochloride but they obtained only chloro derivatives. Several workers have obtained iodo compounds before in presence of various oxidising agents. We have iodinated substituted malonamides in presence of iodic acid as an oxidising agent and have obtained monoiodo and diiodo derivatives from $H_2C(CONHR)_2$ [where R is phenyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-tolyl, 1:4:5-xylyl, 1:3:4-xylyl, *p*-bromophenyl, or hydrogen] and only monoiodo derivatives have been obtained where R is benzyl or ethyl. In the case of malon-diphenylamide, iodine replaces the methylene hydrogen and not the hydrogen of the phenyl group, which is proved by the fact that iodine is readily reduced with potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid (Kurt Meyer, *Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212), whereas iodine attached to the phenyl group is not reduced by this method.

Bromomalon-di-*p*-bromoanilide, bromomalon-di-*p*-tolylamide and bromomalondi-benzylamide also react with iodine in presence of iodic acid and give rise to the corresponding bromoiodo derivatives.

The iodo compounds so obtained are fairly stable and decompose only slowly on long standing. When compared with the corresponding chloro and bromo derivatives, which are quite stable, the instability is attributed to the larger atomic volume of iodine and consequently greater strain being so created in the molecule

EXPERIMENTAL

The compound (2 g.) is dissolved in glacial acetic acid (60 to 90 c.c.) by heating under reflux on a sand-bath and is made to react with iodine (0.4 to 1.6 g.) in the presence of concentrated aqueous solution of iodic acid (0.2 to 0.7 g.). Iodine is slowly absorbed on shaking. When it is completely absorbed, the solution is filtered hot and the filtrate cooled when crystals of the resulting compounds are obtained. They are removed, washed with alcohol or benzene or in some cases with chloroform also and the melting point and solubility in organic solvents determined. They are readily soluble in alcohol, or benzene and in some cases in chloroform and sparingly soluble or insoluble in ether, chloroform and petroleum ether.

TABLE I

Iodo derivatives.	M. p.	Formula.	Iodine.	
			Found.	Calc.
1. Monoiodomalondiphenylamide	Decomposes above 170° and melts at 198°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ I	33.59%	33.42%
2. Diiodomalondiphenylamide	130°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	50.17	50.19
3. Monoiodomalondip-tolylamide	Decomposes above 180° with liberation of iodine; 198°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ I	30.77	31.13
4. Diiodomalondip-tolylamide	136-37°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	47.64	47.56
5. Monoiodomalondio-tolylamide	Decomposes above 170°; 203°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ I	31.33	31.13
6. Diiodomalondio-tolylamide.	Decomposes above 165°; 187-88°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	47.55	47.56
7. Monoiodomalondixylidide (1:4:5)	Decomposes above 190°; 205°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ I	29.27	29.13
8. Diiodomalondixylidide (1:4:5)	Decomposes above 170°; 192-93°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	45.12	45.2
9. Monoiodomalondixylidide (1:3:4)	203-204°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ I	28.98	29.13
10. Diiodomalondixylidide (1:3:4)	108-109°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	45.14	45.2
11. Monoiodomalondip-bromoanilide	Decomposes above 190°; 218°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ I	23.56	23.6
12. Diiodomalondip-bromoanilide	Decomposes above 160°; 205°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ I ₂	38.21	38.24
13. Monoiodomalonamide	Decomposes above 190°; 201-2°	C ₃ H ₅ O ₂ N ₂ I	55.88	55.71
14. Diiodomaloamide	Decomposes above 160°; 198-99°	C ₃ H ₅ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	71.61	71.74
15. Monoiodomalonmonophenylamide	176°	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ I	41.84	41.78
16. Diiodomalonmonophenylamide	140°	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	58.99	59.06
17. Monoiodomalondibenzylamide	171°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ I	31.3	31.13
18. Monoiodomalondietiethylamide	168°	C ₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ I	44.42	44.72
19. Bromoiodomalondip-bromoanilide	Decomposes above 155°; 171°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₃ I	20.57	20.58
20. Bromoiodomalondip-tolylamide	138°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrI	26.02	26.08
21. Bromoiodomalondibenzylamide	109°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrI	26.1	26.08

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